

SHEIKH ZULFIQAR AHMAD NAQSHBANDI

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Abstract.

This article is about the life of the scholars of the tarikhath who lived and worked in our country. In particular, information about the scientific activity and legacy of the leader of the Naqshbandi tarikhath, Sheikh Zulfiqar Ahmad Naqshbandi. His scientific journeys and works are described. The data are broken down into periods. This information is obtained from reliable sources.

Key words

Maveraunnahr, science, enlightenment, religion, inheritance, works, teaching, hadith, tafsir, scholar, hadith scholar, faqih, mufasssir, pious, righteous, zahid, sheikh, mashaikh, hafiz, tradition.

Until the middle of the 15th century AD, there were many ulamas, murshids of sects and Sufism who guided people, taught them knowledge, gave them spiritual education, put beautiful patterns in their inner world, and were beacons of guidance. But with the passage of time, one after another they were released to the eternal world. After their death, people were afraid of not seeing the light-faced beings [9:36].

God's promise is true, there is no doubt about it. Our great Lord will never leave the ummah of his beloved Muhammad, may God bless him and grant him peace, without help. Indeed, it happened. The Muslim world saw the moon rising to the horizon as a beacon of guidance from Jhang in West Punjab [3:121]. His light quickly illuminated the entire horizon. The aching hearts began to drink from the rain of the cloud of mercy. Fear and despair have been replaced by confidence and hope. He was the beloved of the great scholars and the righteous, the leader of Sharia and Tariqat, Maulana Pir Zulfiqar Ahmed Naqshbandi Mujaddidi [8:63].

Birth dates and youth years

Hazrat was born on April 1, 1953 in Jhang, Punjab, India. His father's name was Allah Deeta hafizi Qur'an, and he used to teach Qur'an for the sake of Allah. Every day after Tahajjud, there was a habit of reciting the Qur'an 3-4 times. Hazrat's mother was also a virtuous, righteous and pious woman. He remembers

his mother like this: "I used to sleep with my mother until I was three years old. If I woke up at night, my father would not be with me. Every time I saw my mother praying Tahajjud on the praycarpet. I waited a long time for my mother to finish her prayer. After the prayer, he cried and prayed for a long time. I have never seen anyone cry as much as my mother cried during the Tahajjud prayer. Sometimes he would recite my name and pray, and I would be so happy that I would fall asleep" [7:50].

Primary education and upbringing

His brother Malik Ahmed Ali had a great contribution in the education and upbringing of Hazrat. He was strict and kind. He always kept his brothers away from befriending and talking to naughty children [9:13].

Maulana Zulfiqar Ahmed memorized the entire Quran apart from school and college lessons and became a Quran memorizer. He diligently read Persian and Arabic works, sarf-nahv (Arabic grammar), especially several books on hadith.

Fire of divine love

By this time, Hazrat was greatly influenced by reading "Gunnyatut Talibeen", "Kashful Mahjub" and similar books [4:109]. Sparks of love begin to burn in his heart.

Hazrat was deeply affected by an incident that came to him in the book "Fazaili Zikr" by Shaykhul Hadith Maulana Zakariyya rahmatullahi alayh. In this story, Sirri Saqati, may Allah bless him and grant him peace, says: "I saw His Holiness Jurjani eating dry talkan without chewing it." Then I said, "Well, it's not going to be a power. I said, "How about you bake bread?" Then he said: "Calculating the time spent on chewing bread and eating flour, I learned that a lot of time is wasted. At this time, you can recite "Subhanallah" seventy times. That's why I haven't eaten bread for seventy years," he answers [9:43].

This event affects the sensitive nature of Hazrat to such an extent that he does not let the mention of "SubhanAllah" come from his tongue, day or night. As a result, Hazrat made a habit of eating less and sleeping less. For two and a half years, Hazrat did not stop mentioning "Subhanallah". Every day for two years, he prayed to God and prayed to God: "O God, let me meet a perfect piri murshid that means Mentor in tasawuf of islam and grant me his conversation" [5:88].

Divine grace

Allah Ta'ala has never rejected an unbiased supplication, nor will He ever do so. At the age of 18, a remarkable incident happened to Hazrat. Maulana Zulfiqar Ahmed was in Itikaf in the mosque, after the tahajjud prayer, after the dhikr, about an hour before dawn, he fell asleep on the place of prayer and saw Hazrat Abu

Bakr Siddique, may God be pleased with him, in his dream. He put his fingers on the soul of Hazrat and said: "Allah...", "Allah..." "Allah...". Hazrat woke up, and his whole body was shaking.

Master attitudes

After this incident, Hazrat begins to feel a strange flavor in his prayers, dhikr, and recitations. His heart begins to beat harder, but in a pleasant way. He even binds his breasts for several days. In the end, he tells his university friends, Mr. Muhammad Amin, about the incident. He went to Lahore and took advice from Sheikh Wajihuddin. They recommend him to write a letter to the piri-kamil (Mentor in tasawuf of islam) Abdullah rahmatullahi alayh. After a few days, the letter received a reply with the following content: "What is known is that your heart has become enlightened. Immediately learn from a teacher, Allah will guide hundreds of thousands of people with you. If you don't take a teacher, the accursed devil can plot you."

After reading this letter, Hazrat Zulfiqar Ahmad went to Mawlana Sayyid Zawwar Hussain Shah, the famous Naqshbandi sect of that time, and took him as a teacher and received education. After the death of his teachers, he continued to study under Hazrat Khwaja Ghulam Habib, a mature murshid of the Naqshbandi sect of that time.

In 1983, he received the status of khalifa from his teacher and began to teach people based on the Naqshbandi sect. As a result, he becomes one of the mature sheikhs of the Naqshbandi sect [7:11].

Indeed, the blessings of the saints are true. A few years ago, Khwaja Mawlana Abdullah said: "Allah will guide hundreds of thousands of people using you as a reason." Nowadays, the students and followers of Hazrat Sheikh Maulana Zulfiqar Ahmad Naqshbandi have exceeded one million people.

Hazrat explains the problems of our time according to the teachings of the Naqshbandi sect with skillful and modern examples. Sheikh Hazrat's speeches and lectures are diltartar and aimed at reforming spiritual education. People listen to Hazrat's lectures and conversations with tears in their eyes and sincerely repent of their sins. Most importantly, they make it a habit to follow the Sunnah in life.

The works of Hazrat Sheikh Zulfiqar Ahmad are loved and read hand in hand among readers. Due to his mastery of religious and worldly sciences, and his fluent lectures in several foreign languages, he is widely promoting the teachings of the Naqshbandi sect in the 21st century, not only in Asia, but also in Europe and the United States. Hazrat has visited more than seventy countries, especially Uzbekistan several times. In memory of his travels, he wrote a book called "Lohur

se to hake Samarkandu Bukhara" (From Lahore to the soil of Samarkand and Bukhara) [9:45].

Sheikh Zulfiqar Ahmad Naqshbandi married the younger daughters of Hazrat Khwaja Muhammad Abdulmalik Siddiqui, who were memorizers of the Qur'an. Two sons were born from them: Maulana Pir Habibullah Naqshbandi and Maulana Saifullah Naqshbandi.

Places of education

- 1967 - high school
- 1971 - Special Secondary Education (College) in Punjab
- 1976 - Electrical engineering specialty in Lahore
- 1990 - advanced training in his field in Sweden

The path of religious education

- He memorized the entire Qur'an from his father.

- Jamiya Rehmaniya studied Hadith in Jahaniya Mandi University in full Hadith course.

- Jamia Qasim ul-Ulum also participated in the Hadith course in Multan University.

- 1971 Shaykh Mawlana Sayyid Zavwar Husain Shah receives lessons from the Naqshbandi sect and Sufism.

- 1983. Receives education in Naqshbandiya sect and Sufism from Hazrat Khoja Ghulam Habib, may God bless him and grant him peace.

Written books

"Divine love", "Ishqi Rasul", "Lives of our beloved", "Levels of leech", "Leech bodies", "Zikr of the Naqshbandiya order", "Silsil of Naqshbandiya sheikhs", "Healing of the heart", "Peace of heart", "Useful knowledge", "An exemplary woman", "How to avoid sins?", "The role of a woman in the development of a man", "Do not despair", "The importance of faith", "Methods of purification of the heart", "Conditions of forgiveness", "Reformative education for women", "An exemplary view of marriage", "A guide for Muslim women", "Mysticism and leech", "Dignity is of good character", "Preparation for death", "From Lahore to the soil of Bukhara and Samarkand", "Kindness of Islam to women" [5:125].

"Ilohiy ishq", "Ishqi Rasul", "Habibimiz hayotlari", "Suluk darajalari", "Suluk maqomotlari", "Naqshbandiya tariqatining zikrlari", "Naqshbandiya shayxlari silsilasi", "Dil davosi", "Qalb xotirjamligi", "Foydali ilm", "Namunali ayol", "Gunohlardan qanday saqlanamiz?", "Erkak kamolotida ayolning o'rni", "Noumid bo'lmang", "Imonning ahamiyati", "Qalbni poklash usullari", "Mag'firat qilinish shartlari", "Ayollar uchun islohiy tarbiyalar", "Turmushning namunali ko'rinishi",

“Muslima ayollar uchun yo‘riqnoma”, “Tasavvuf va suluk”, “Odobli nasibalidir”, “O‘limga tayyorlanish”, “Lahurdan Buxoro va Samarqand tuproqlarigacha”, “Islomning ayollarga mehribonligi” [5:125].

In conclusion, it can be said that in the history of human development, there were such individuals whose activities not only went beyond the borders of the local cultural area, but also crossed the borders of the eras and became a part of the global process in the development of ideas. Their works, like all rare phenomena, embody the most valuable aspects of previous experiences, determine the progress of scientific thought of society and spiritual culture that will take place in the next many centuries. Such a great figure is the undisputed Sheikh Zulfiqar Ahmad Naqshbandi.

Based on the material and conclusion of the article, the following suggestions can be made:

1. It is appropriate to study the life and heritage of Sheikh Zulfiqar Ahmad Naqshbandi, who played an important role in the formation and development of the Naqshbandi sect.

2. It is important to study the scientific activity and heritage of this scientist and show its importance in solving certain problems.

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